

Preparation of *o*-Hydroxy-Ketoanils

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o-Hydroxy ketoanils have been prepared by condensing 2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone with aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and α -naphthylamine, using anhydrous zinc chloride as a condensing agent. Their absorption spectra in ultra-violet, visible and infra-red regions were taken. They are found to be chelating agents for copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II).

THE anils have been prepared by different workers¹⁻⁴. In our investigation 2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone has been condensed with aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and α -naphthylamine, using zinc chloride as condensing agent. The derivative of the anils have been prepared.

The absorption spectra of anils in ultra-violet and visible region shows three absorption maximas as recorded in Table 1. The values suggest that the para-substitution in benzene nucleus attached to

nitrogen has no appreciable effect on the position of absorption maxima but when the naphthyl group is attached to nitrogen, a dampening of the absorption maxima is observed. This may be due to the bulkiness of the group. The anils are yellow in colour, giving yellow coloured solution in alcohol and other organic solvents, but they do not show any characteristic absorption maxima in the blue region. The trailing portion of the absorption spectra which extends into the blue region of the spectrum cause a yellow or yellowish-orange colour.

The infrared spectra of these anils were recorded. They show -C=N- absorption band between

1625-1620 cm^{-1} and substitution at para position in the benzene nucleus attached to nitrogen atom or at carbonyl-carbon has no effect on the position of -C=N- band. Fabian Legrand and Poirier⁵ had shown that -C=N- absorption in the open chain system occurs within the range 1960-1940 cm^{-1} , but the lowering in value may be due to conjugate chelating in the system. The shifting of the -C=N- absorption bands to lower frequency due to conjugate chelation (Hydrogen bond formation) is similar to the frequency shifts of carbonyl group with an *o*-Hydroxy substituent⁶.

These anils are found to be chelating agents for copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II).

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone anil :

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone was prepared by the Fries reaction of *p*-cresyl benzoate⁷.

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (0.1 mole), base (0.1 mole) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g.) were mixed and heated on oil bath at 160° for ½ hr and then the temperature was raised to 180°. It was kept at this temperature for 5 mins and was allowed to cool. The anil was extracted with chloroform.

TABLE 1. ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF ANILS

<i>y</i>	Ist Max. nm (log ϵ)	IInd Max. nm (log ϵ)	IIIRD Max. nm (log ϵ)
1. Phenyl	226.0 (4.0548)	267.0 (3.7829)	345.0 (3.5520)
2. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	228.0 (4.3312)	267.0 (4.0375)	345.0 (3.8552)
3. <i>p</i> -Anisyl	233.0 (4.3593)	260.0 (4.1021)	345.0 (3.9246)
4. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	234.0 (4.3400)	267.0 (4.0985)	345.0 (3.7542)
5. <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	234.0 (4.3558)	267.0 (4.1299)	345.0 (3.8875)
6. <i>p</i> -Naphthyl	—	—	345.0 (3.8342)

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The chloroform was distilled out from the extract and the product was crystallised from ethanol. Several anils and derivatives which have been prepared are as follows :

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone anil, m.p. 160°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 65°;

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone(*p*)tolyl, m.p. 110°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 62°;

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone(*p*)anisil, m.p. 162°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 66°;

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone(*p*)chlorophenyl-anil m.p. 124°, benzoyl derivative, m.p. 187°;

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone(*p*)bromophenyl-anil, m.p. 82°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 63°;

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone(α)naphthil, m.p. 140°, benzoyl derivative, m.p. 156°.

All compounds described above gave correct carbon hydrogen analysis.

The absorption spectra of the anils in ultra-violet visible region were taken in ethanol using Unicchem-spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra were taken on I.R.5 using nujol as medium.

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